

Project Features

- Environment (E)
 - Server (E1)
 - * Connection (E1.1)
 - Web (E1.1.1)
 - FTP (E1.1.2)
 - SQL (E1.1.3)
 - * TEsk Execution (E1.2)
 - * TEsk Configuration (1.3)
 - Data (2)
 - * Integrity (E2.1)
 - * Availability (E2.2)
 - * Durability (E2.3)
- Architecture (A)
 - Security (A1)
 - * Interface (A1.1)
 - User Authentication (A1.1.1)
 - Cryptography (A1.1.1.1)
 - Digital Certificates (A1.1.1.2)
 - Tokens (A1.1.1.3)
 - Data Availability (A1.1.2)
 - * Persistence (at the database level) (A1.2)
 - Data Integrity (A1.2.1)
 - Efficiency (A2)
 - * Performance (A2.1)
 - Simultaneous Access (A2.1.1)
 - Operational Performance (A2.1.2)
 - * Size (A2.2)
 - Table Size (A2.2.1)
 - Memory Constraints (A2.2.2)
 - Cache Requirement (A2.2.3)
- Integration (I)
 - Legacy (I1)
 - * Functionality Access (I1.1)
 - * Communication Methods (I1.2)
 - * Data Exchange (I1.3)
 - Third-Party (I2)
 - * Services (I2.1)
 - APIs (I2.1.1)
 - Frameworks (I2.1.2)
 - Hybrid Development (I2.1.2.1)

- Ionic (I2.1.2.1.1)
 - Electron (I2.1.2.1.2)
 - Security (I2.1.2.2)
 - JWT (I2.1.2.2.1)
 - Auth (I2.1.2.2.2)
- * Configuration (I2.2)
 - Libraries (I2.2.1)
 - Requests (I2.2.1.1)
 - Persistence (I2.2.1.2)
 - Communication (I2.2.1.3)
- Method (M)
 - Technique (M1)
 - * Train Predictive Model (M1.1)
 - * Code Blockchain Network (M1.2)
 - Public (M1.2.1)
 - Private (M1.2.2)
 - Consortium (M1.2.3)
 - * Implement AI Algorithm (M1.3)
 - Validation (M2)
 - * Client Data Requirement (M2.1)
 - * System Deployment (M2.2)